

Innovation Trajectories and Future Prospect of Electric Vehicles in Mountain Logistics

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Abstract

This study examines innovation trajectories and technological advancements in electric cars using a comprehensive dataset of 23,290 patents related to electric cars. We use Latent Dirichlet Allocation topic modeling to identify eight key technological areas, including electric vacuum pumps, electric drive systems, electric car body structures, electric car charging methods and infrastructure, intelligent control systems, electric power control, battery technology and power supply, and rotor shaft design and assembly. The findings indicate significant patent activity, especially in China, highlighting its role as a global leader in electric car innovation. This study provides strategic insights for researchers and practitioners, enabling informed decision-making.

Keywords: Electric cars, mountains, topic modeling

Introduction

The global automotive industry is transforming significantly to combat climate change, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and address fossil fuel depletion (Kabeyi & Olanrewaju, 2022). Central to this process is the focus on electric cars, autonomous driving systems, and connected car technologies, driven by companies' increasing investments in new technologies, government policies, and stringent CO₂ regulations (Sonar et al., 2023). Among these recent developments, electric cars can be considered a general-purpose technology (GPT) due to their potential to catalyze transformative changes across multiple sectors beyond transportation. In manufacturing, advancements in electric cars are driving battery production, lightweight materials, and sustainable

supply chains. Integrating electric cars with autonomous systems is advancing artificial intelligence, sensor technologies, and V2X communication, vital for traffic management and safety. Additionally, electric car-related innovations are reshaping investment strategies in finance, emphasizing green bonds and sustainability-linked financing. Overall, the impact of electric cars goes beyond transportation, fostering innovation and promoting efficiency and sustainability globally.

Despite a positive outlook for electric cars, several challenges hinder their development and widespread adoption. These include high costs due to expensive battery components (Yuan & Li, 2021). The long charging times, limited component lifespans (Alanazi, 2023), and environmental concerns related to producing and disposing of electronic components, especially mining and recycling rare earth metals (Balaram, 2019). In addition, inadequate charging infrastructure contributes to "range anxiety" (Saravade et al., 2022), while existing power grids may not support the increased load from electric cars, raising concerns about grid stability and the need for renewable energy sources (Tavakoli et al., 2020). In light of these challenges, extensive research and investment are also being directed from academia and industry. Some studies focused on technological solutions either on the electric cars' components, like battery technologies (Liu et al., 2022), or the infrastructure (Metais et al., 2022). Other studies use secondary data (e.g., patents) analysis and systematic reviews to map technological diffusion (Yuan & Li, 2021) and the business process of electric cars (Anthony, 2017).

The abovementioned studies, however, often focus on specific aspects of electric cars, neglecting the broader interconnected landscape. This fragmented approach is problematic as it fails to capture how individual technologies within the electric car ecosystem co-evolve. Without this broader viewpoint, there is a risk of overestimating the impact of isolated innovations and developing misplaced optimism about the overall development state of electric cars. Moreover, this scenario poses at least three practical challenges. First, organizations struggle to prioritize investments due to limited visibility into technological dynamics. This makes it hard to focus efforts and increases the risk of missing growth opportunities. Second, policymakers encounter obstacles in designing impactful support measures and making informed decisions on budget allocations, incentives, and regulations for a green transition. Third, potential users face difficulty identifying the most suitable solutions due to limited knowledge of available options. Therefore, considering electric cars as GPT, this study contributes to the literature and practice by providing a comprehensive analysis that captures the intricate interplay among various components: adopting a holistic perspective enables the understanding of cross-sector synergies and feedback loops and illustrates how progress in one area stimulates advancements in others. Additionally, this approach guides strategic partnerships across industries, fostering collaborations that accelerate the development of complementary technologies. With this in mind, this study aims to shed light on the following research question (RQ):

RQ. What is the state of development in the field of electric cars?

In this regard, we conduct a comprehensive analysis of 23,290 electric car-related patents using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) technique. This method is valuable for uncovering technological trends, interdependencies, and key players in innovation, which traditional patent analysis (like descriptive statistics and IPC code analysis) overlooks. LDA analyses word co-occurrence in patent texts to reveal hidden topics and patterns, enhancing our understanding of the electric car innovation landscape (Blei et al., 2003; Momeni & Rost, 2016). This approach supports strategic decision-making for

researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders in areas like policy formulation, R&D, and intellectual property strategies.

The analysis identifies eight key thematic areas within electric car technologies. Four of these have attracted the most interest: electric car charging methods and infrastructure, battery technology and power supply, intelligent control systems, and electric car body structures. The results further indicate that China is at the forefront of patenting activity, establishing itself as the leading country propelling advancements in this field.

Data source and methodology

This study utilized the Derwent Innovation Index (DII) database as the primary data source for analysis. Renowned for its extensive coverage and detailed indexing, DII contains over 14.3 million inventions from nearly 60 patent-issuing authorities worldwide, ensuring high-quality data (DII, 2024; Sampaio et al., 2018). The database's long historical record also helps mitigate potential time and country biases, providing a comprehensive perspective on patenting activity (Sampaio et al., 2018).

Regarding search string formulation, we employed a focused keyword search strategy to ensure a comprehensive and unbiased data collection. This approach allows us to capture innovations across all relevant electric car-related technological fields, providing a holistic view of the industry's ongoing advancements. For this purpose, we select keywords that represent the different terminologies used by industry and academia to describe electric cars and their related technologies. The keywords "Electric Car", "Electric Automobiles", "Plug-in cars", "Zero-Emission cars", "Green Cars", and "Plug-In Hybrid Electric car". The keyword research considered the title, abstract, and claims to gather a more comprehensive set of documents. This search yielded 23,484 patent documents.

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive statistics offer a foundational overview of R&D efforts in electric car technologies, revealing key trends and distribution patterns in this fast-evolving field. First, we examined yearly patent trends to gauge annual technological output, allowing us to track the pace of innovation and identify periods of heightened R&D activity. Second, we analyzed the distribution of patents across International Patent Classification classes to gain insights into specific technological focus areas (Daim et al., 2006). Third, we analyzed market dominance by country to highlight regional innovation dynamics and identify global hotspots in electric car technology development (Zhou et al., 2014). Finally, we conducted a collaboration network analysis of inventors and assignees to map relationships within the ecosystem, identifying key players and influential contributors who drive advancements in the field.

Topic Modeling using Latent Dirichlet Allocation

Following the initial cleaning, the textual content of the patents, including titles and abstracts, was further pre-processed for topic modeling. The preprocessing steps at this stage include tokenization (breaking down the text into individual tokens or words), lowercasing (converting all tokens to lowercase to ensure uniformity), stemming and lemmatization (reducing words to their root forms), and stop word removal (e.g., of custom keywords: claims, copyright, protect etc.) (Blei et al., 2003; Maier et al., 2018). Additionally, non-alphanumeric characters and too-short tokens were filtered out to maintain data quality. The pre-processed text was then converted into a numerical format

suitable for topic modeling using the Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method, which helps to emphasize important words in the dataset while restraining common words that appear across many documents (Ramos, 2003).

To perform the topic modeling, we resorted to the Latent Dirichlet Allocation technique, a probabilistic model that identifies hidden themes within a document set by grouping frequently co-occurring words (Blei et al., 2003). The LDA model was trained on the pre-processed patents, iteratively refining the topic-word and document-topic distributions to best represent the observed data. Once the model converged, each patent was allocated to the topic with the highest likelihood, as determined by its internal topic distribution. To facilitate interpretation, we displayed the most frequent words within each topic, providing a set of high-probability keywords that clarified the underlying themes in the assigned patents. This topic extraction process was supported by the Gibbs sampling algorithm, a widely used method for approximating posterior distributions in LDA (Griffiths & Steyvers, 2004). To obtain a representative number of topics, we ran our model iteratively and measured U_{mass} coherence scores, in which the lower value represents the better number of topics; the number of topics that yielded lower coherence values is ten, with a score of -1.31. For our analysis, we used a Python script and libraries, including "pandas," "openpyxl," "nltk," "gensim," and "spacy." The extracted topics were interpreted and labeled based on identified keywords and by analyzing samples of patent documents (Murdock & Allen, 2015). To strengthen and validate the outcomes of this procedure, we refined the results iteratively, incorporating feedback from five three academic experts in the field who reviewed and adjusted topic labels. During this process, we observed considerable overlap between certain topics—an expected result given the technological focus of the data. This redundancy was addressed by applying agglomerative clustering, grouping topics with similar keywords and themes. The clustering algorithm was applied to the word-topic distribution from the LDA model, with each topic initially treated as a separate cluster. This approach allowed us to reduce the number of topics from ten to eight by merging topics.

Results

Temporal distribution of patent applications

The line graph in Figure 1 illustrates the temporal trend in electric car-related patenting activities from 2000 onward. The data reveal a steady increase, followed by a significant acceleration around 2010, indicating a growing focus on sustainable transportation technologies. For example, patent applications rose from 66 in 2000 to a peak of 2,229 in 2016, while patent publications increased from 64 in 2000 to 2,581 in 2018. This surge is likely driven by several key factors.

Figure 1: Temporal Trend of Patent Applications and Publications

Patent applications distribution by IPC class

Figure 2 details the top IPC codes relevant to electric car technologies in which code B60, representing general vehicle technologies, is the most prominent category accounting for 34%. Within this category, a significant portion (20%) is attributed to B60L, which covers electric propulsion systems and related drive technologies. In addition to vehicle-specific aspects, the chart highlights key areas related to electric power distribution and management. For instance, H02 (generation, conversion, or distribution of electric power) constitutes 15% of electric car-related patents. Electrical components are also well-represented, with H01 accounting for 12% of patents, including subcategories like H01M, dedicated to batteries and fuel cells. This reflects the crucial role of energy storage and management in advancing electric car technology, as efficient battery systems are essential for electric cars' performance and range. Additionally, the G06 category (5%) addresses data processing and computational technologies linked to autonomous driving, diagnostic systems, and other smart car features.

Figure 2 Patent distribution by IPC classifications

Distribution of patent applications by country

The distribution of electric car-related patent applications by country, highlighting the leading contributors to electric car technological innovation and disparities in patent activity across nations. China holds a dominant position, accounting for 58% (12,585) of total patents, followed by South Korea and Japan with 10% (2,079) and 8% (1,635) of patents, respectively. The United States ranks fourth with 6% (1,201) of patents, while Germany and other countries, including India, Taiwan, and Brazil, make up the remaining percentage. This concentration of electric car-related patents among China, South Korea, and Japan underscores the significant role of these three Asian countries in driving electric car innovation. China's leadership, in particular, is bolstered by extensive investments in electric car technology and government policies that actively promote industry-specific advancements and broader technological growth (Wu et al., 2021). These initiatives support sustainable transportation efforts and reflect a broader strategy to position China as a global leader in high-tech sectors.

Collaboration network between assignees

Network analysis of assignees' collaborations provides insights into the strategic partnerships that drive innovation, identifying key players and structures that facilitate knowledge sharing and resource allocation (Breschi & Lissoni, 2005). This approach is instrumental in dynamic fields like electric cars, where collaboration and knowledge exchange are pivotal in accelerating technological progress (Fleming & Sorenson, 2001). Figure 3 shows a network visualization of assignees who have made significant contributions to the technological advancement of electric cars.

Starting with the assignees, LG Chemical Ltd. emerges as a prominent hub with the highest number of connections (39) and the highest betweenness centrality (0.2337), underscoring its role as a critical bridge within the network. This central position enables LG Chemical to connect otherwise separate actors, thereby facilitating knowledge transfer and promoting the diffusion of innovation across diverse areas of electric car technology. Other influential assignees, such as Bosch GmbH, Chery Automobile Co., and State Grid Corp China, act as strategic intermediaries. Bosch, with 20 connections and a betweenness centrality of 0.0712, connects multiple actors across the network, promoting information flows within and beyond its immediate partnerships. Chery Automobile, with 17 connections and a betweenness centrality of 0.0661, plays a similar role in connecting regional or specialized nodes, integrating niche innovations into the broader electric car landscape. State Grid Corp China, with 37 connections and a close betweenness centrality (0.2139), highlights the influence of government-led entities within the network, as it supports the exchange of knowledge across both public and private sectors. Closeness centrality values across the network, generally between 0.2 and 0.3, indicate a well-integrated structure that allows assignees to benefit from direct and intermediary access to other entities. This interconnectedness enables rapid engagement with new developments and collaborative opportunities. For example, Shenzhen Optimum Battery Co. stands out with a high closeness centrality (0.2649), suggesting a strong position to rapidly access and share innovations in battery technologies. Bosch's closeness centrality (0.2414) similarly highlights its accessibility to other players, enhancing its ability to connect with and support the flow of innovations across the network. The rank metric further underscores the hierarchical organization within the network. Entities like LG Chemical (rank 0.0164) and Bosch (rank 0.0087) hold influential positions, while others, such as University Southeast (rank 0.0066) and BAIC BJEV Co. Ltd. (rank 0.0065), play more specialized but still impactful roles. This

hierarchy supports a balance between global knowledge exchange, driven by key hubs, and focused contributions from niche players, creating a robust and adaptable ecosystem. In summary, the electric car innovation network, with central players like LG Chemical, Bosch, Chery Automobile, and State Grid Corp China, demonstrates a moderately centralized structure that enables both widespread knowledge sharing and targeted contributions from specialized entities. This arrangement fosters a collaborative environment conducive to sustained technological progress and adaptability within the sector.

Figure 3 Collaborative network of EV inventors and assignees

Content analysis of technological areas

Using the LDA method and subsequent dendrogram clustering, we identified eight distinct technological areas within the electric car landscape: electric car charging methods and infrastructure, battery technology and power supply, intelligent control systems, electric car body structure, electric drive systems, design and assembly of rotor shafts, electric vacuum pumps, and electric power control. Each theme highlights a specific technological field and its contribution to the ongoing development and innovation of electric cars. To assess the future potential and current development stage of each domain, we analyzed specific patent quality indicators that reflect different aspects of influence, foundation, and integration within the technological landscape. In particular, we employed three indicators: the Count of Citing Patents (CoCP), the Count of Cited References - Non-patent (CoCRNP), and the Count of Cited References - Patent (CoCRP). The CoCP measures the number of subsequent patents that cite a given patent, indicating its influence and relevance within the field; patents with a high CoCP are frequently referenced, suggesting significant industry recognition and impact. The CoCRNP represents the number of non-patent references (such as academic papers or technical reports) cited by a patent, indicating a strong foundation in scientific research and interdisciplinarity. Finally, the CoCRP measures the number of other patents referenced within each patent, highlighting the degree of technological integration and reliance on prior patented knowledge within each domain.

Table 1 below provides a summary of the thematic classifications, associated keywords, citing and cited references, and percentage shares, illustrating the technological areas driving the evolution of electric cars.

Table 1: The latent technological areas driving the evolution of electric cars

Topics	Naming of electric car technology	Top ten keywords	#of patents	% share	CoCP	% share	CoCRNP	% share	CoCRP	% share
[1, 8]	Electric car charging method and infrastructure	charging, vehicle, electric, information, system, device, module, wherein, claim, unit electric, power, time, charging, vehicle, method, step, energy, according, station	4477	21.62%	25480	39,27%	2945	47,43%	20815	25,33%
[3,9]	Battery technology and power supply	electrode, battery, cell, material, wherein, secondary, layer, lithium, according, method battery, power, electric, voltage, connected, module, circuit, system, current, supply	4638	22.39%	15682	24,17%	1871	30,13%	20227	24,61%
4	Intelligent control system	control, vehicle, electric, signal, value, method, according, speed, controller, wherein	2229	10.76%	8232	12.69%	566	9.12%	10355	12.60%
5	EV body structure	plate, electric, frame, body, connected, wheel, device, claim, according, connecting	3848	18.58%	7363	11.35%	263	4.24%	17376	21.14%
6	Electric drive system	motor, wheel, shaft, gear, electric, driving, system, vehicle, generator, connected	2758	13.32%	3387	5.22%	171	2.75%	5264	6.40%
10	Design and assembly of a rotor shaft	layer, member, cell, unit, apparatus, rotor, assembly, case, coil, direction	1081	5.22%	2730	4.21%	323	5.20%	5621	6.84%
2	Electric vacuum pump	valve, heat, cooling, pressure, pipe, hole, tank, sealing, pump, inlet	402	1.94%	1296	2.00%	41	0.66%	1629	1.98%
7	Electric power control	electric, line, contact, apparatus, position, device, circuit, wire, switch, characterized	1279	6.18%	711	1.10%	29	0.47%	903	1.10%

Note: CoCP = Count of Citing Patents; CoCRNP = Count of Cited Refs - Non-patent; CoCRP = Count of Cited Refs - Patent

Conclusion

This study examines electric cars as a general-purpose technology and their role in driving innovation across sectors such as energy storage and transportation. Key academic implications include establishing an empirical foundation through analysis of 23,290 patents, providing insights into core electric car technologies and development paths for future research. Second, highlighting different national innovation models, particularly China's state-supported ecosystem versus private-led models, emphasizes these approaches' impact on technological progress. Third, uncovering complex technological interdependencies within the electric car sector using advanced techniques like Latent Dirichlet Allocation, showcasing the potential of topic modeling to reveal new areas for research and deeper insights into the innovation landscape.

Furthermore, the study highlights the maturing state of specific areas within electric car technology, offering industry stakeholders essential insights for strategic planning. As foundational technologies like battery efficiency and charging infrastructure, companies can shift focus from pioneering R&D to enhancing production efficiency and expanding infrastructure. This transition allows for better resource allocation to refine established technologies, strengthening competitiveness in a reassessing market. Additionally, analyzing maturing technologies helps organizations identify necessary skills and knowledge, guiding workforce training, targeted R&D, and strategic partnerships for effective resource alignment. The relatively low production of electric car technologies in Western regions indicates the need for targeted policies, such as tax incentives for R&D and funding for industry-academia collaborations, to boost innovation. Moreover, insights into mature technologies can aid policymakers in prioritizing support for scalability and integration. By optimizing infrastructure—expanding charging networks, incorporating renewable energy, and improving battery efficiency—policymakers can promote technology transfer and bolster the economic impact of the electric car sector, ensuring sustainable growth in a shifting global market.

This study analyzes the technological landscape of electric cars but has some limitations. While patents are commonly used to study innovation, not all advancements are captured in patent data, and patents may lag behind current developments. The focus on patents limits the view on social, environmental, and economic implications. Future research could incorporate diverse data sources like industry projects, government initiatives, market stats, and stakeholder input through interviews and surveys for a more comprehensive understanding of electric car advancements. Additionally, our keyword-based approach may have missed relevant patents, so employing more advanced methods could yield a more inclusive dataset. Using LDA for topic identification might also overlook insights in patent sections beyond titles and abstracts. Future studies could apply more sophisticated techniques to capture technological themes fully. Lastly, our use of citation analysis and descriptive statistics might miss influential factors like patent age or examiner characteristics. More robust indicators could enhance the analysis in future research.

Acknowledgments

This research has been carried out within the PNRR research activities of the consortium iNEST (Interconnected North-East Innovation Ecosystem) funded by the European Union Next-GenerationEU (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 D.D. 1058 23/06/2022, ECS_00000043). This manuscript reflects only the Authors views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

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